

STUDYING SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL, PSYCHOLOGICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL SOURCES RELATED TO THE PROBLEM IN FUTURE STUDENTS

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Annotation. *This article analyzes the pedagogical aspects of social philosophy in the educational process. The importance of the basic concepts and principles of social philosophy in the formation of the human personality in pedagogical processes is highlighted. Also, the pedagogical mechanisms of philosophical approaches that serve to develop social consciousness, master social values, and comprehensively develop the personality in the educational process are studied. The author gives recommendations on the practical application of the ideological and methodological foundations of social philosophy in the pedagogical process. The article considers the current issues of forming social consciousness and responsibility in the educational process. Education and upbringing, as one of the main factors of social development, play an important role in the formation of the human personality. This process includes not only the formation of knowledge and skills, but also the development of social consciousness and responsibility. From this point of view, the study of pedagogical aspects of social philosophy serves to increase the effectiveness of the educational system. Social philosophy provides a solid theoretical basis for illuminating the issues of human spiritual development, social values, and the development of consciousness in the educational process.*

Keywords: *Education, social philosophy, pedagogical aspects, social consciousness, personal development, pedagogical process, methodological approach, social values.*

Annotatsiya. *Mazkur maqolada ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonida ijtimoiy falsafaning pedagogik aspektlari tahlil qilingan. Ijtimoiy falsafaning asosiy tushunchalari va tamoyillari pedagogik jarayonlarda inson shaxsini shakllantirishdagi ahamiyati yoritilgan. Shuningdek, ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonida ijtimoiy ongning rivojlantirish, ijtimoiy qadriyatlarni o'zlashtirish hamda shaxsni har tomonlama kamol topishiga xizmat qiluvchi falsafiy yondashuvlarning pedagogik mexanizmlari o'rganilgan. Muallif, pedagogik jarayonda ijtimoiy falsafaning g'oyaviy-metodologik asoslarini amaliy qo'llash bo'yicha tavsiyalar bergan. Maqolada ta'lim va tarbiya jarayonida ijtimoiy ong va mas'uliyatni shakllantirishning dolzarb masalalari ko'rib chiqilgan. Ta'lim va tarbiya jamiyat taraqqiyotining asosiy omillaridan biri sifatida inson shaxsini shakllantirishda muhim o'rin tutadi. Mazkur jarayon nafaqat bilim va ko'nikmalarni shakllantirish, balki ijtimoiy ong va mas'uliyatni rivojlantirishni ham o'z ichiga oladi. Shu nuqtai nazardan, ijtimoiy falsafaning pedagogik aspektlarini o'rganish ta'lim-tarbiya tizimining samaradorligini oshirishga xizmat qiladi. Ijtimoiy falsafa ta'lim jarayonida insonning ma'naviy kamoloti, ijtimoiy qadriyatlar va ongning rivojlantirish masalalarini yoritishda mustahkam nazariy asosni taqdim etadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Ta'lim-tarbiya, ijtimoiy falsafa, pedagogik aspektlar, ijtimoiy ong, shaxs kamoloti, pedagogik jarayon, metodologik yondashuv, ijtimoiy qadriyatlar.*

***Аннотация.** В статье анализируются педагогические аспекты социальной философии в процессе образования. Подчеркивается значение основных понятий и принципов социальной философии в формировании личности человека в педагогическом процессе. Также изучены педагогические механизмы философских подходов, которые служат развитию общественного сознания, усвоению социальных ценностей, всестороннему развитию личности в процессе воспитания. Автор дал рекомендации по практическому применению идейно-методологических основ социальной философии в педагогическом процессе. В статье рассматриваются актуальные вопросы формирования социального сознания и ответственности в процессе обучения и воспитания. Образование и обучение как один из основных факторов развития общества играют важную роль в формировании человеческой личности. Этот процесс включает в себя не только формирование знаний и умений, но и развитие общественного сознания и ответственности. С этой точки зрения изучение педагогических аспектов социальной философии служит повышению эффективности образовательной системы. Социальная философия дает прочную теоретическую основу для освещения вопросов духовного развития человека, социальных ценностей, развития сознания в образовательном процессе.*

***Ключевые слова:** Образование, социальная философия, педагогические аспекты, общественное сознание, развитие личности, педагогический процесс, методический подход, социальные ценности.*

The basis of any educational system in society is the fate of the future generation and the interests of the people. In the realization of such interests, the personal qualities of the younger generation play a leading role. The qualities of the growing younger generation are directly related to the type, volume and quality of education provided to them today. The pedagogical methods created by mankind to form communicative qualities in children are not without shortcomings.

Therefore, such methods are constantly evolving, and all educators and teachers are looking for methods that meet the requirements. As a result of these studies, various approaches to the educational process have emerged among Uzbeks.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoyev, said, "We will mobilize all the forces and capabilities of our state and society so that our youth can become independent-thinking, highly intellectual and spiritually capable people who are not inferior to their peers in any field in the world, mature and be happy." - these words mean that the future of children is bright. From this point of view, the formation of communicative qualities in children based on an axiological approach is relevant.

The path from the strategy of actions aimed at ensuring democratic development to the Development Strategy at the new stage of Uzbekistan's development is inextricably linked with the need to further improve interpersonal relations in society. The essence of these changes is reflected in the consciousness of society, the self-awareness of people and, on this basis, the transition from a strong society to a strong state.

The 70th goal of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 dated January 29, 2022 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" is called "Improvement of state policy on youth", which emphasizes "Educating young people in a spirit of patriotism, civic spirit, tolerance, respect for laws, national and universal values, capable of

resisting harmful influences and trends, with firm beliefs and views on life. This means that young people need to live based on national and universal values, based on the requirements of society.

Today, great reforms are being carried out in the field of preschool education, but despite various approaches to the educational process, it is difficult for children to adapt to school education and effectively communicate with their peers and others. The level of formation of communication in older preschool children is associated with the period of early infancy. During this period, the child enters the world of people, masters speech signs. He gets acquainted with the norms of communication between people and the rules of behavior, simple manifestations of human speech activity. A preschool child enters the world of social relations in the early period of development. Through communication with family members and educators, he gradually learns the norms of behavior. However, during this period he cannot understand his own actions. Under the influence of speech and communication, the child's inner world begins to form. The child's form of interaction with adults changes, he reacts to events and phenomena around him. As a result, children begin to master communicative activity.

Older preschool children enter into communication with adults, their vocabulary expands in connection with the processes around them. The child learns to communicate as a person. This period is very important for the formation of communicative qualities. Because the concept of "I" is formed in children, that is, individuality emerges, self-expression takes precedence. He learns to express his opinion freely. In individualization, changes are observed related to the needs of children to communicate. At the same time, children gradually begin to enter into public relations. The issue of intensive preparation of preschool children for school education by forming communicative qualities is considered urgent.

In the upbringing of communicative qualities in children, the spiritual and moral experience of previous generations is of great importance, ensuring the continuity and continuity of the past with the present, preserving national and universal values, through which each nation, first of all, preserves the continuity of its spiritual, ethnic psychology, traditions, customs and character. The historically formed high national values of the Uzbek people, such as humanity, national pride, and the promotion of spirituality, help overcome difficulties in the development of society. Humanity in mutual relations is rooted in deep respect for family members and relatives, and in a person's loyalty to his conscience and duty. In this way, the younger generation strives for humane relations on the path to a bright future. In order to combat the negative vices existing in society, including unkindness, selfishness, and immorality, we need to teach children the mechanisms for correcting traditions and customs in universal, national, secular, moral, aesthetic, social, family, historical, religious, spiritual, and political processes.

The purest feelings of a person, the first life concepts and ideas are formed primarily in the family through the love and affection of parents, sweet words that come from the heart. The spiritual criteria and views that determine the character, nature, and worldview of a child - the foundation of sacred concepts such as goodness, nobility, kindness, and morality - are formed in the family. This once again means that the use of family values and reliance on national and universal values in the formation of communicative qualities in children based on an axiological approach is of great importance.

Developing the relationship between the educator and the student based on our national values, further improving customs and traditions at the preschool education stage is one of the urgent tasks of today. As experts have noted, traditions are of great importance in cultivating personal qualities in students, improving their spiritual and educational competence, and having a

unique educational effect in forming a fully mature personality. Both the educator and the student must master and be able to apply in practice national and universal values that ensure the effectiveness of communication. Such factors include the following:

1. Taking into account universal values.
2. Good knowledge of national customs and practices:
 - a) respect for elders and honor for younger ones;
 - b) special respect for women;
 - c) the educational environment in the family: the relationship between spouses, the relationship of parents to their children, the relationship of children to their parents;
 - d) the relationship and treatment of teachers to their students, and in turn, the relationship of students to their teachers;
 - e) the relationship of leaders to ordinary people;
 - f) the relationship and treatment of kindred spirits;
 - g) the relationship between neighbors and neighbors.
3. The circle of thought, level of knowledge, worldview of the interlocutors.
4. The mental state of the interlocutors.
5. The social environment in society: peace, tranquility, economic situation, interethnic harmony.
6. Awareness of national identity and respect for representatives of other nationalities.
7. Acquire the skills to overcome "communicative barriers".
8. Master the ethics and etiquette of communication.
9. Practical mastery of verbal and nonverbal means of communication.
10. Technological approach to the communication process.
11. Constantly improving one's communication culture, striving for a communicative ideal.

Raising children in a spirit of respect for adults and honor for younger ones in their youth is one of our true national values. Relationships between people are important in this. In particular, family members and relatives need to be friendly with each other, strengthen ties of kinship, sympathize with each other in their misfortunes and share in each other's joys. Because children who are raised to be kind and compassionate to each other in their youth will be kind to each other when they grow up. From this point of view, based on an axiological approach, we have identified the following tasks in researching the topic of pedagogical and psychological mechanisms for the formation of communicative qualities in students:

- to prepare children from an early age for free thinking, to help them understand the meaning of life, to form self-management and self-control;
- to introduce children to national, universal values, the rich spiritual heritage of our Motherland, to form a desire to acquire cultural and secular knowledge, to develop skills, to cultivate and enrich them, and to form aesthetic concepts;
- to identify the capabilities of each child, to develop them, to implement them in various areas of activity centers. To create conditions for the emergence and further support of children's creativity and talent;
- to form in children the norms of humane behavior, including the formation of etiquette of mutual understanding, kindness, compassion, intolerance of racial and national discrimination;
- patriotism, secular thinking, learning to communicate with people living in our society, loyalty to one's people, state, always being ready to defend it, respectfully treating the symbols of

the Republic of Uzbekistan and other states, educating the younger generation in the spirit of loyalty to the Constitution, Flag, Coat of Arms, National Anthem, President of Uzbekistan;

- educating respect for community morality and rules of life, developing a sense of social responsibility that characterizes the unique features of the child;

- forming the qualities of a creative approach to labor, which is considered the highest value in life by instilling the elements of labor;

- educating and developing the desire for a healthy lifestyle, forming the desire to become a worthy family owner;

- teaching children to think freely, independently.

When we say value, we first of all understand the phenomena of nature and the benefits of society that serve the interests and goals of the nation, people and social groups that are important for man and humanity, and therefore are valued and appreciated by them.

An analysis of the literature on the study of pedagogical aspects of social philosophy in the educational process shows that this topic has been studied by many leading scientists. The relationship between social philosophy and pedagogical sciences, their importance in the formation of the personality, and the mechanisms of adaptation to the needs of society have been considered in various scientific approaches.

The works of Uzbek scientists, in particular, such researchers as Abdullayeva[1], Nurmatov[6], are devoted to the study of the formation of national values in education and their harmonization with the principles of social philosophy. Their research emphasizes the socialization of the individual and the importance of the social environment in the educational process.

Among Russian scientists, V. S. Lazarev and N. Yu. Krupskaya's works are devoted to the issues of forming social consciousness. They emphasize the need for philosophical approaches to adapting the individual to the social environment in the educational process. Lazarev develops theoretical foundations for the development of social responsibility and gives practical recommendations for their application in the pedagogical process.

In foreign literature, for example, authors such as P. Freire indicate the formation of social consciousness and values as the central task of the educational process. P. Freire emphasizes the importance of developing critical thinking in the educational process.

In the current period, the works of European scientists on the issues of integrating social philosophy into the educational process are of great importance, in particular, researchers such as E. Gellner and A. MacIntyre. They study the issues of transforming the education system in the context of socio-cultural changes. Gellner showed the impact of changes in social values and their impact on personality development.

Among Uzbek scientists, Karimov and Soliyeva conducted research on the application of social philosophy in the national education system. They emphasize the role of national culture and traditions in the formation of social values.

According to the results of the analysis, the pedagogical aspects of social philosophy are considered an urgent issue not only theoretically, but also practically. The literature serves as a theoretical basis for studying this topic, and also creates a platform for developing practical recommendations for education. At the same time, it is determined that there is still a need for more in-depth empirical research on the topic.

Values have social characteristics and are formed and developed in the process of practical activity of people. Values arise in connection with a set of things and phenomena that are useful

for people's activities in various spheres, primarily in the field of production and labor. Then, gradually, as a result of the child's activity, they begin to function as a relatively independent sphere. Natural and social phenomena are included in the list of values as a result of human activity. It is inappropriate to evaluate natural and social phenomena that do not satisfy human interests, needs, and do not correspond to their dreams, aspirations, and ideals as values.

The communicative qualities of children include the ability to adequately perceive various information, their ability to influence others, especially peers, self-assessment and self-esteem, as well as knowledge of the norms of communicative codes. Eastern scholars have also substantiated the importance of communication and conversation with people in the development of a person in their pedagogical views.

Abu Nasr Farobi, who is recognized as the second teacher in the world, in his work "On the Achievement of Happiness", puts forward the idea that "a person cannot achieve perfection alone. He needs contact with others, their support or relationships. Education can only be achieved through words and teaching." Indeed, in the development of a child's personality, his effective communication with others, his worldview and communication play an important role

Communicative skills include meaningful speech, perception, understanding, observation and changing the information provided according to its content. Communicative skills come in two forms depending on their implementation. These are: intrasubjective (internal) or extrasubjective (external) communicative skills, that is, information producers.

In the formation of communicative skills, a creative type of speech activity is manifested. In such situations, children also develop communicative speech. It is necessary for communication participants to have communicative skills, that is, to understand and imagine oral and written speech, to perceive it, to use it in the implementation of personal communication tasks, etc.

Conclusion. Thus, the structural communicative qualities of children's speech include such features as correctness, richness, purity. The functional communicative qualities of speech include its accuracy, logicity, expressiveness, usability, expressiveness and expediency of speech. The analysis of this topic shows that in the process of applying an axiological approach to the formation of communicative qualities in children, it is possible to improve their morals, spirituality and relationships by using educational influence derived from the national values of the Uzbek people.

Especially in the upbringing of the younger generation, it is necessary to connect national values with advanced technologies in order to raise a national patriot, self-confident person in each child. If the educator in the process of education and upbringing cultivates communicative qualities in children in the spirit of their nation, then this will become the main basis for the process of the child's attitude to the whole world, to his own life and to the lives of others with the worldview of an educated person. Indeed, humane education based on an axiological approach creates a strong foundation for the development of the child.

The study shows that the introduction of pedagogical principles of social philosophy in the educational process not only serves the development of the individual, but also has a positive impact on the development of society. The widespread implementation of these approaches in pedagogical practice will serve as an important factor in increasing the competitiveness of the national education system in the future.

REFERENCES

1. Sh. Mirziyoyev. We will continue our national development path with determination and take it to a new level. "Uzbekistan", 2016. P. 146.

2. Bocharnikova M. A. // Young Student. 2009. - No. 8 (8). - P. 130-132 p.
3. Zununov A. et al. History of Pedagogy: Textbook for Academic Lyceums and Vocational Colleges. - T.: "Sharq", 2002. - 192 p.
4. Komilova D.A. Theories on the Formation of Communicative Competence in Preschool Children. // Modern Education. 2021. No. 4.
5. Abdullayeva, D. (2020). The Importance of National Values in the Educational Process. Tashkent: Fan Publishing House.
6. Freire, P. (1970). Pedagogy of the Oppressed. New York: Continuum.
7. Gellner, E. (1996). Conditions of Liberty: Civil Society and Its Rivals. London: Penguin.
8. Karimov, A. (2021). Issues of forming social values in the Uzbek education system. Tashkent: Ma'naviyat.
9. Krupskaya, N. Yu. (1929). On pedagogy and education. Moscow: Gosizdat.
10. Nurmatov, O. (2019). Social philosophy and pedagogy: integrated approaches. Samarkand: Center for Scientific Research.
11. Lazarev, V. S. (2017). Public knowledge in pedagogy: theory and practice. Moscow: Nauka.
12. Soliyeva, M. (2022). Methodological foundations of social philosophy in the pedagogical process. Tashkent: Publishing House of the National University of Uzbekistan.